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Parametric Analysis of Operating Parameters of Additive Manufacturing of Various Wedged Geometries by Laser Directed Energy Deposition

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Abstract

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This article presents a parametric analysis on the gray areas of Laser Directed Energy Deposition (DED) for the formation of creating a wedged geometry. To create the wedged shape-shaped structure through additive manufacturing presents unique challenges due to the intricate interplay of various control parameters. In addition, using the finite element analysis (FEA) tool ANSYS for simulating temperature distributions during laser additive manufacturing. The study investigates the influence of key parameters like laser power, laser scan speed, and laser beam diameter over the formation of varying wedged angle geometry by Laser Additive Manufacturing (LAM) of the LAM by DED. In addition, this work includes FEA analysis for optimizing the model of different wedged geometry. The result of this investigation shows that laser beam diameter of 1.5mm and the scan speed of 10mm/sec at laser power of 1000W gives the optimum combination of the parameters for the formation of wedged geometry. This approach successfully predicts the significance of operating parameters for metal deposition without self-melting at the narrow geometrical area.

Introduction

In Industries, continuous demand to design flexible, efficient, and able to produce complex components with high performance is required. Laser Additive Manufacturing (LAM) possesses several unique features that contribute to its growing demand in various industries. LAM allows unique objects with unique features to be made directly from computer data [1]. The fundamental principle of a LAM system involves the layer-wise deposition and solidification of material to build a 3-D digital model. Also, develop a controlled application of heat through a laser to selectively melt and solidify material layer by layer, following the digital design of the object. The LAM process allows for the formation of complex materials and customized geometries with

reduced material waste. It is used in different industries, including as tooling, automotive, aerospace, and healthcare [2-3].

LAM has the potential to eliminate many traditional manufacturing steps and streamline the production process in various ways. LAM presents several advantages over conventional subtractive manufacturing techniques, such as reduction of material waste, design flexibility, customization, reduced lead times, reduced assembly requirements, low energy consumption and capability to produce functionally graded parts. Also, it is a convincing choice for refurbishing applications, and its characteristics make it well-suited for component repairing, reconditioning, and rapid prototyping because of low heat input, material compatibility, laminated dilution, layer-wise additive processes, near-net shape components, and accuracy with precision [4]. Recently, the applications to produce functionally graded materials (FGMs) [5-6], biomedical, lightweight structures, and porous materials [7-8] with a significant development in additive manufacturing.

Laser Additive Manufacturing (LAM) system consists of controlled powder, a high-powered laser source, real-time monitoring, and robotic systems for motion, integrated with computer-aided design and control in an optional controlled atmospheric chamber that contributes to its capabilities in creating 3D objects layer by layer [9]. The diameter of LAM (0.1-3 mm) is measured as the focal distance in a perpendicular direction. The process involves feeding metallic powder (2 to 30 g/min) into a molten pool created by a laser beam to build up a three-dimensional object layer by layer. argon gas is commonly used as both a shielding gas and a powder carrier gas. Different metals or alloys may require different shielding gases, and the optimization of gas parameters is crucial for achieving high-quality additive manufacturing results [10].

Edson Costa et al. suggested that, through the use of laser-based layer manufacturing, it is possible to achieve the direct fabrication of metal products with high density and excellent mechanical properties. This work finding signifies a successful exploration of laser-based layer manufacturing for direct fabrication of metal products with specific qualities. This discovery has implications for advancing the field of additive manufacturing, offering a viable and effective approach for creating metal components with high density and superior mechanical properties. Such advancements are valuable across industries, including aerospace, automotive, medical, and more, where high-performance metal parts are often required [11].

Researchers have been suggesting that laser manufacturing is being considered as a favorable alternative for the fabrication of Colmonoy-6 bushes, several cylindrical titanium samples with different dimensions, and it is specifically highlighted for its advantages over GTAW and laser cladding techniques in terms of saving in machining and cost [12-13]. Some research are demonstrated various aspects of Selective Laser Melting (SLM) fabricated parts that aims to provide a deeper understanding of the current status of process outcomes for the material. In addition, the study indicates that more research is needed, particularly in the areas of process parameters and building patterns, to achieve desirable grain structures and properties to enhance the understanding of the process outcomes. Research activities in recent times have mainly focused on examining how to optimize SLM parameters and building strategies for achieving desired grain structures and properties in the fabricated parts [14-17].

Some research has analyzed the influence of foaming agents on laser-based manufacturing processes. Also, investigated scan speed, effected on the manufactured material, powder feed rate, and the optimization of the manufacturing process with three-dimensional finite element analysis being done while laser power was constant to create an empirical solution [18-20]. Laser-based manufacturing is presented as a concept that aims to provide a holistic parameter incorporating

both laser scan speed and powder feed rate. This can potentially streamline the analysis and optimization of additive manufacturing processes [21].

In the experimental analysis, researchers investigated how the position and orientation of parts impact dimension accuracy and surface quality in the context of additive manufacturing. In the context of lightweight design, typical basic shapes have been identified and then fabricated using Laser Additive Manufacturing (LAM). These structures include thin walls, bars, and boreholes with varying diameters. The fabrication process involved building these structures in different orientations [22-23]. Also, describes a microstructural examination that was conducted to reveal fine dendritic growth in the direction of wall building. The applications in ultramodern systems, particularly in Advanced Ultra Super Critical Power Plants with extreme duty conditions, highlight the relevance of this work in advancing materials for high-performance applications. Additionally, it mentions the deployment of laser-marking treatment before the deposition of each layer [24-25].

It is in these contexts, a review of existing studies investigating the effect of several random process parameters on thin wall structure formation, the thermal distribution is being analyzed and parameters are optimized. But no literature is found in the study on gradually increasing area i.e., wedged shape geometry. In such geometries at the end, there is the minimum area to build. Formation of that part of the geometry is difficult because there is always a chance of self-melting of the edged part and due to this, need of controlling the running parameters of the LAM DED is required. Therefore, the goal of this work is to investigate the optimum value of the operating parameters and to form possible scan strategies for deposition in a wedged shape.

Materials and Methods: -

Material Powder characteristics

Gas atomized 316L stainless steel powder with a particle size range of 56 to 107 μm is used as powder feedstock. It is well-suited for additive manufacturing applications, having good flow ability, packing density, corrosion resistance, and mechanical properties. The typical chemical composition of 316L stainless steel is shown in Table 1

Table 1: Chemical Composition of 316L SS

Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	P	C	S
10.84	2.37	1.07	0.44	0.026	0.006	0.006

Stainless steel grade 316L, often referred to as marine grade stainless steel or A4 stainless steel. It is the low carbon version of 316 stainless steel, having melting temperature in the range of 1375 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Stainless steel typically contains iron as its base metal, with chromium, nickel and molybdenum with small quantities of silicon, phosphorus and sulfur. The addition presence of molybdenum makes it distinguished for its exceptional corrosion resistance properties, particularly in aggressive environments such as marine settings and chemical processing plants, where it provides better corrosion resistance, with respect to localized corrosive attack by chlorides and to general corrosion by reducing acids, such as sulfuric acid.

It is commonly used in chemical and petrochemical industry, food processing equipment, pharmaceutical equipment, medical devices, jewellery, luxury watches, potable water piping, and waste water treatment, in marine applications and architectural applications near the seashore or in urban areas. Due to its favorable properties and extensive use, 316L SS is one of the widely used alloys in AM techniques, including DED.

Method Details

The setup of system is illustrated in Fig. 1, wedged shape geometry of material 316L stainless steel (SS) with dimensions of 50 mm × 50 mm and angles of 5°, 10°, and 15° are being analyzed. It sounds like the study is examining how variations in the angle of the wedged shape affect temperature distribution. Out of 50 mm length, 5 mm has been left from the wedged corner because the material thickness at this part of the geometry is very less so the probability of self-melting of the material during deposition is high. It is considered that a heat source beam having power of 1000W, 1500W and 2000W is scanning the path with scan speed of 2 mm/sec, 5mm/sec and 10mm/sec with the varying beam diameter of 1mm, 1.5 mm and 2 mm. For the calculation of global energy density (GED) powder mass flow rate (PMFR) of 10 gm/sec is taken. Over lapping laser beam is considered 50%.

Figure 1: Schematic Arrangement of LDED System

In the investigation for finding thermal distortion during heat source movement is carried out in terms of Transient Thermal analysis by using the FEA tool ANSYS a moving heat source over a geometry approach based on heat flux applied over a fixed path is used. Simulating temperature distributions during laser additive manufacturing of wedged geometry involves employing numerical method. The temperature distribution at the laser path, the amount of heat flux produced during laser scanning, and the amount of global energy density produced are all calculated using this method, which solves the heat conduction and constitutive equations throughout the process domain using a FE method. The user-defined input parameters with the appropriate initial and boundary conditions are used as input. The temperature values are utilized to estimate the temperature generated above the laser beam's melting point and the material interface at the thin section of the wedged portion of the geometry as shown in Fig. 2. Several combinations of processing parameters are used for the simulation of temperature distribution over deposited geometry. The simulation results are analyzed and the LAM process parameters are optimized.

Figure 2: Geometry of Wedged Angle of 10°

Result and Discussion-

For proper analysis of finding the effect of governing parameters, in total 81 iterations are performed on ANSYS 18.0. To get the optimum value of parameters, iterations are performed over following parameters in Table 2.

Table 2: Laser Parameters Used

Laser Power (Watt)	1000	1500	2000
Laser Beam Diameter (mm)	1	1.5	2
Scan Speed (mm/sec)	2	5	10

(a) 5° Wedge Angle

(b) 10° Wedge Angle

(c) 15° Wedge Angle

Figure 3: Graph between Laser Power, Wedge Angle, Scan Speed and Maximum Temperature Generated

To analyzing the flow rate of a powdered substance, perform at a rate of 10 gm/sec. Analyzing the effects of various parameters, such as powder flow rate, on the maximum temperature generated, maximum heat flux generated, and global energy density is essential for optimizing laser processing operations. Optimizing these parameters contains finding the right balance to achieve desired outcomes such as minimizing defects, improving mechanical properties, and increasing productivity.

When considering different wedge angles (e.g., 5, 10, and 15 degrees) as shown in Figure 3. For formation of geometry having wedge angle of 5° on using laser power of 1000 W, it is observed that maximum temperature of 1599.8 °C is reached at the beam diameter of 1.5 mm over scan speed of 2mm/sec. Understanding the combinations of scan speed and beam diameter that result in temperatures exceeding the melting temperature of 316L stainless steel is crucial for optimizing laser processing operations, particularly in applications like laser welding or additive manufacturing as reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameter Combination Generating Temperature Above Melting Point

S. No.	Scan Speed (mm/sec)	Laser beam Diameter (mm)
1	2	1.5
2	2	2
3	5	1.5
4	5	2
5	10	1.5
6	10	2

However, for the combinations of scan speed and beam diameter listed below in Table 4, the temperatures generated are safer, presumably below the melting temperature of 316L stainless steel:

Table 4: Parameter Combination Generating Temperature Below Melting Point

S. No.	Scan Speed (mm/sec)	Laser beam Diameter (mm)
1	2	1
2	5	1
3	10	1

Using a smaller beam diameter (1 mm) along with varying scan speeds (2 mm/sec, 5 mm/sec, and 10 mm/sec) results in temperatures that are safer for the material, likely preventing it from reaching its melting point. This information can guide the optimization of laser processing parameters to achieve the desired outcome while ensuring the safety and integrity of the material being processed.

Figure 4: Graph between Laser Power, Wedge Angle, Scan Speed and Maximum Heat Flux Generated

While in case of formation of geometry of 10° scan speed of 2 mm/sec, 5 mm/sec and 10 mm/sec at beam diameter of 1.5 mm are generating temperature higher than the melting temperature. When we move towards the formation of wedged geometry of 15° laser power of 1000W is the safer power to work at all possible combinations of the parameters, in addition to that the power of 1500 W at 5 mm/sec of scan speed on beam diameter of 1.5 mm also gives a safe combination. At scan speeds of 2 mm/sec, 5 mm/sec, and 10 mm/sec with a beam diameter of 1.5 mm, temperatures higher than the melting temperature are being observed during the formation of the geometry. This suggests that these combinations are producing excessive heat, likely due to the rapid delivery of energy to the material.

When forming a wedged geometry, a laser power of 1000 W is determined to be safer across all possible combinations of parameters. Additionally, a power of 1500W is deemed safe

when combined with a scan speed of 5 mm/sec and a beam diameter of 1.5 mm. These findings indicate that when forming the wedged geometry, a laser power of 1000 W is generally safer to use across a range of scan speeds and beam diameters is illustrated in Figure 4. However, at a specific combination of parameters (scan speed of 5 mm/sec and beam diameter of 1.5 mm), a higher power of 1500W can also be employed safely.

The amount of heat transferred per unit area per unit time (Heat Flux), is a critical parameter in the process of DED in additive manufacturing. The heat flux during this process affects several aspects of the resulting material, including: the size and shape of the molten pool formed during the deposition process. A higher heat flux can result in a larger and deeper molten pool, influencing the fusion characteristics and material flow. The cooling rate of the molten metal influences the grain structure of the deposited material. Higher heat flux can lead to rapid cooling, resulting in finer grain structures, while lower heat flux may allow for slower cooling and the formation of larger grains. Heat flux also affects the residual stresses and distortion in the final part. Rapid heating and cooling can lead to higher levels of residual stress and increased distortion, which can affect dimensional accuracy and mechanical properties.

The grain structure and residual stress introduced by the heat flux significantly impact the mechanical properties of the DED samples. Finer grain structures often result in improved mechanical properties such as strength and fatigue resistance. Therefore, controlling the heat flux is crucial for achieving desired material properties in DED-manufactured components. It requires careful consideration of parameters is given in Table 5. For the geometry having wedge angle of 5⁰ degrees, following data are observed for heat flux which ranges from a minimum of 75.378 W/mm² to a maximum of 1423 W/mm².

Table 5: Parameter Combination Generating Heat Flux at 5⁰ Wedge Angle

Heat Flux Generated (W/mm²)	Laser Power (Watt)	Scan Speed (mm/sec)	Laser Beam Diameter (mm)
75.378 (Minimum)	1000	10	1
1423 (Maximum)	2000	10	1.5

This observation highlights the significant influence of process parameters, that, higher laser power and smaller beam diameter tend to result in higher heat flux, as evidenced by the maximum value observed. For the geometry that having wedge angle of 10⁰ degrees, Table 6, showing observations of value of parameters that generated heat flux ranges from range of 229.16 W/mm² to 757.06 W/mm².

Table 6: Parameters Generating Heat Flux at 10⁰ Wedge Angle

Heat Flux Generated (W/mm²)	Laser Power (Watt)	Scan Speed (mm/sec)	Laser Beam Diameter (mm)
229.16 (Minimum)	1000	2	2
757.06 (Maximum)	2000	10	1

Similar to the previous observation, the higher laser power, higher scan speed, and smaller beam diameter tend to result in higher heat flux values. For 15⁰ wedge angle it is observed that, the heat flux generated ranges from a minimum of 99.282 W/mm² to a maximum of 537.59

W/mm². The heat flux values associated with specific combinations of process parameters for the generating heat flux are tabulated in Table 7.

Table 7: Parameters Generating Heat Flux at 10° Wedge Angle

Heat Flux Generated (W/mm ²)	Laser Power (Watt)	Scan Speed (mm/sec)	Laser Beam Diameter (mm)
99.282 (Minimum)	1000	5	1.5
537.59 (Maximum)	2000	2	1

Once again, this observation highlights the influence of process parameters on heat flux generation during the DED process. As seen in previous cases, higher laser power, higher scan speed, and smaller beam diameter tend to result in higher heat flux values. However, the optimization of these parameters should consider the specific requirements of the application and the material being processed to achieve desired results.

Figure 5: Graph between Global Energy Density Produce, Beam Diameter and Laser Power

Global Energy Density (GED) is one of the crucial parameters in additive manufacturing processes like DED as shown in figure 5. GED refers to the total amount of energy delivered to the material during the deposition process per unit volume or unit mass. It's a key factor in determining the thermal history of the deposited material, which significantly influences its microstructure, mechanical properties, and overall performance [26]. Mathematically GED can be calculated as:

$$GED = \frac{P}{m \cdot v \cdot d_{beam}^2}$$

Where, P is Laser power, m is Powder mass flow rate (PMFR), v is Laser scan speed and d_{beam} is the diameter of the laser beam. A higher energy density typically results in faster heating and cooling rates, which can influence the grain structure, phase transformation, and residual

stresses within the deposited material. Controlling the energy density is essential for achieving desired material properties, such as hardness, strength, and ductility, as well as minimizing defects like porosity and cracking. As the graph showing the influence of Laser power on the generation of GED as, higher laser power generally results in a higher energy input to the material that increases the GED. The PMFR affects the amount of material being deposited per unit time, which can influence the overall energy input but here in the study it is taken as 10gm/sec. The amount of lower scan speed means the heat source dwells longer on each point, allowing for more energy transfer to the material, hence potentially increasing GED. The value of laser beam diameter also influences GED in terms of focusing the energy, smaller laser beam diameter focuses the energy into a smaller area, leading to higher energy density at that spot, thus potentially increasing overall GED. By the observation we find that, the combination of higher laser power, lower scan speed, and smaller laser beam diameter leads to higher GED values. This combination allows for more energy to be concentrated in a smaller area for a longer duration, resulting in a higher overall energy density.

The graph indicates that the highest GED value observed is up to 100,000 J/(kg/sec mm³). This indicates a significant amount of energy being delivered per unit volume of material per unit time, highlighting the efficiency and intensity of the deposition process under the specified parameters. Optimizing these parameters to achieve the desired GED is essential for controlling the thermal characteristics, microstructure, and mechanical properties of the deposited material.

Figure 6: Graph showing Effect of Laser Power on Temperature Generation as per the Wedged Angle

It is acknowledged that, laser power plays a significant role in heat generation during additive manufacturing processes as shown in Fig 6. Higher laser power means more energy is being delivered to the material, leading to increased heating. It is noted that the amount of temperature generated is directly proportional to the laser power applied. This is consistent with the understanding that higher laser power results in more heat being generated, leading to higher temperatures in the material being processed. From the graph it is also observed the in case of wedged geometries of 5⁰ degrees, the amount of temperature generated is higher compared to wedge geometries of 10⁰ and 15⁰ degrees. This is due to the shape and angle of the geometry that can affect heat dissipation and the distribution of energy within the material. Sharper angles, such as 5⁰, concentrate more energy in a smaller area, leading to higher temperatures. Wedged geometries with smaller angles might have less surface area exposed to the laser, allowing for more energy to be concentrated in a smaller region, leading to higher temperatures. The thermal

conductivity and heat transfer properties of the material also influence temperature distribution. Materials with lower thermal conductivity might retain more heat, resulting in higher temperatures.

Figure 7: Graph showing Effect of Beam Diameter on Temperature Generation as per the Wedged Angle

It is observed in Fig 7, regardless of the specific combination of laser power, scan speed, and beam diameter, a beam size of 1.5 mm consistently produces the highest temperature across all wedge angle geometries. Additionally, a beam diameter of 1 mm results in the least temperature, while a 2 mm beam diameter leads to medium-range temperature generation. This observation proposes that the beam diameter has a significant impact on temperature distribution and heat input during the additive manufacturing process, particularly in the context of different wedge angle geometries. Some potential observations are a larger beam diameter may distribute the energy over a larger area, leading to less concentrated heat input compared to a smaller beam diameter. As a result, the temperature generated with a 2 mm beam diameter falls within a medium range. The optical properties of the laser beam, such as its focal point and intensity profile, can vary with beam diameter. A 1.5 mm beam diameter may optimize energy delivery to produce higher temperatures compared to other beam sizes. The interaction between the laser beam and the material surface can be influenced by the beam diameter, affecting heat absorption and temperature generation. A 1.5 mm beam diameter may enhance energy absorption and conversion into heat, leading to higher temperatures.

Different wedge angle geometries may have varying surface areas and geometrical features, which can influence heat dissipation and temperature distribution. The observed trend across all geometries suggests a consistent relationship between beam diameter and temperature generation. Understanding these relationships between beam diameter and temperature generation is crucial for optimizing process parameters in additive manufacturing to achieve desired temperature profiles, material properties, and part quality. Adjusting the beam diameter appropriately can help control temperature distribution and enhance process stability and efficiency.

Figure 8: Graph showing Effect of Scan Speed on Temperature Generation as per the Wedged Angle

From the Figure 8, graph present slower laser scan speeds indeed often result in higher heat and temperature generation, while faster scan speeds can lead to lower heat input and temperature. This happens because of the reason that, slower scan speeds mean that the laser beam spends more time at each point on the work piece, allowing more energy to be deposited into the material. This prolonged exposure results in higher heat input and temperature generation at each spot. Also, with slower scan speeds, there is more time for heat to accumulate and spread within the material, leading to higher temperatures in the scanned area. This is also due to the reason that, slower scan speeds increase the contact time between the laser beam and the surface, allowing for more energy transfer and heat generation. Conversely, faster scan speeds reduce this contact time, resulting in less heat input and lower temperatures. Scan speed also affects the heat dissipation, faster scan speeds may not allow sufficient time for heat to dissipate from the scanned area, resulting in lower overall temperature generation.

Hence, optimizing scan speed is essential for controlling temperature distribution, thermal gradients, and material properties during the additive manufacturing process. It involves balancing heat input, cooling rates, and process efficiency to achieve desired outcomes in terms of part quality, microstructure, and mechanical properties.

Conclusion-

This study revealed the influence of the process parameters laser power, laser scan speed and laser beam diameter on the formation of wedged geometry with different angles of the material 316L SS samples additively manufactured by DED. The work has also offered a plotting graph between temperature, heat flux, global energy density generation, and various processing parameters is a key step in understanding the relationships between these variables and optimizing the additive manufacturing process. The results suggest that, a laser power of 1000W is generally considered safer across a range of scan speeds and beam diameters. This choice ensures stable processing conditions and minimizes the risk of issues such as excessive heat input, material spattering, or self-melting. However, it is also noted that, at a specific combination of parameters—specifically, a scan speed of 5 mm/sec and a beam diameter of 1.5 mm. a higher power of 1500W can also be employed safely. This indicates that under certain conditions where a higher energy input is

required to achieve desired process outcomes, such as faster melting rates or deeper penetration, increasing the laser power can be beneficial without compromising process stability or part quality.

Controlling heat flux is crucial for optimizing the additive manufacturing process and achieving desired material properties and part quality. It involves carefully balancing parameters such as for all the wedged geometries of considered angles laser power of 1000 W, scan speed of 2 mm/sec and beam diameter of 2 mm generates minimum heat flux while the laser power of 2000 W, scan speed of 10 mm/sec and beam diameter of 1 mm always generates the maximum heat flux, which can mitigate the risk of defects, minimize distortion, and enhance the overall performance and reliability of additively manufactured components. In the observation it is also found that, the higher laser power, lower scan speed, and smaller laser beam diameter leads to higher GED values. This combination allows for more energy to be concentrated in a smaller area for a longer duration, resulting in a higher overall energy density.

Due to the shape and angle of the geometry that can affect heat dissipation and the distribution of energy within the material from the results, it is also observed the in case of wedged geometries of 5° degrees, the amount of temperature generated is higher compared to wedge geometries of 10° and 15° degrees. Beam diameter of 1 mm results in the least temperature generation, while a 2 mm beam diameter leads to medium-range temperature generation. The 1.5 mm beam diameter produces optimum energy delivery to produce higher temperatures compared to other beam sizes. Slower scan speeds, get more time for heat to accumulate and spread within the material, leading to higher temperatures in the scanned area hence the scan speed of 2 mm/sec produces more temperature than the higher scan speeds.

In conclusion, this work successfully identified the optimal processing parameters for DED of 316L SS. Process parameter optimized by finding their effects on the maximum temperature, heat flux and global energy density generation over different wedge angle geometries of the deposited material are essential for the manufacturing of parts without its self-melting at the lower material section.

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